

Supplement: Sustainable data analysis with Snakemake

November 3, 2020

S1 Readability

Statements in Snakemake workflow definitions fall into seven categories:

1. a natural language word, followed by a colon (e.g. `input:` and `output:`),
2. the word “rule”, followed by a name and a colon (e.g. `rule convert_to_pdf:`),
3. a quoted filename pattern (e.g. `"{prefix}.pdf"`),
4. a quoted shell command,
5. a quoted wrapper identifier,
6. a quoted container URL
7. a Python statement.

Below, we list the rationale of our assessment for each category in Figure 3:

1. The natural language word is either trivially understandable (e.g. `input:` and `output:`) or understandable with technical knowledge (`container:` or `conda:`). The colon straightforwardly shows that the content follows next. Only for the wrapper directive (`wrapper:`) one needs to have the Snakemake specific knowledge that it is possible to refer to publicly available tool wrappers.
2. The word “rule” is trivially understandable, and when carefully choosing rule names, at most domain knowledge is needed for understanding such statements.
3. Filename patterns can mostly be understood with domain knowledge, since the file extensions should tell the expert what kind of content will be used or created. We hypothesize that wildcard definitions (e.g. `{country}`) are straightforwardly understandable as a placeholder.
4. Shell commands will usually need domain and technical knowledge for understanding.

5. Wrapper identifiers can be understood with Snakemake knowledge only, since one needs to know about the central tool wrapper repository of Snakemake. Nevertheless, with only domain knowledge one can at least conclude that the mentioned tool (last part of the wrapper ID) will be used in the wrapper.
6. A container URL will usually be understandable with technical knowledge.
7. Python statements will either need technical knowledge or Snakemake knowledge (when using the Snakemake API, as it happens here with the `expand` command, which allows to aggregate over a combination of wildcard values).

S2 Design patterns

Figure S1 shows advanced design patterns which are less common but useful in certain situations. For brevity only rule properties that are necessary to understand each example are shown (e.g. omitting log directives and shell commands). Below, we explain each example in detail.

Scatter/gather processes (Figure S1a). Snakemake’s ability to employ arbitrary Python code for defining a rule’s input and output files already enables any kind of scattering, gathering, and aggregations in workflows. Nevertheless, it can be more readable and scalable to use Snakemake’s explicit support for scatter/gather processes. A Snake-make workflow can have any number of such processes, each of which has a name (here `someprocess`). In this example, the rule `scatter` (line 4) splits some data into n items; the rule `step2` (line 8) is applied to each item; the rule `gather` (line 14) aggregates over the outputs of `step2` for each item. Thereby, n is defined via the `scattergather` directive (line 1) at the beginning, which sets n for each scatter/gather process in the workflow. In addition, n can be set via the command line via the flag `--set-scatter`. For example, here, we could set the number of scatter items to 16 by specifying `--set-scatter someprocess=16`. This enables the user to better scale the data analysis workflow to its computing platform, beyond the defaults provided by the workflow designer.

Streaming (Figure S1b). Snakemake allows to stream output between jobs, instead of writing it to disk (see subsection 2.5.4 in the main document). Here, the output of rule `step1` (line 1) and `step2` (line 7) is streamed into rule `step3` (line 13).

Non-file parameters (Figure S1c). Data analysis steps can need additional non-file input in the form of parameters, that are for example obtained from the workflow configuration (see subsection 2.1 in the main document). Both input files and such non-file parameters can optionally be defined via a Python function, which is evaluated for each job, when wildcard values are known. In this example, we define a lambda expression (an anonymous function in Python), that retrieves a threshold depending on the value of the wildcard sample (`w.sample`, line 7). Wildcard values are passed as the first positional argument to such functions (here `w`, line 7).

```

a
1 scattergather:
2   someprocess=8
3
4 rule scatter:
5   output:
6     scatter.someprocess("scattered/{scatteritem}.txt")
7
8 rule step2:
9   input:
10    "scattered/{scatteritem}.txt"
11   output:
12    "transformed/{scatteritem}.txt"
13
14 rule gather:
15   input:
16    gather.someprocess("transformed/{scatteritem}.txt")

b
1 rule step1:
2   output:
3     pipe("hello.txt")
4   shell:
5     "echo hello > {output}"
6
7 rule step2:
8   output:
9     pipe("world.txt")
10  shell:
11    "echo world > {output}"
12
13 rule step3:
14   input:
15    "hello.txt",
16    "world.txt"
17   output:
18    "hello-world.txt"
19   shell:
20    "cat {input} > {output}"

c
1 rule step:
2   input:
3     "data/{sample}.txt"
4   output:
5     "results/{sample}.txt"
6   params:
7     threshold=lambda w: config["threshold"][w.sample]
8   shell:
9     "some-tool -x {params.threshold} {input} > {output}"

d
1 pepfile: "pep/config.yaml"
2 pepschema: "schemas/pep.yaml"
3
4 rule all:
5   input:
6     expand(
7       "results/{sample}.somerresult.txt",
8       sample=pep.sample_table["sample_name"]
9     )

e
1 def get_results(wildcards):
2   with checkpoints.qc.get().output[0].open() as f:
3     qc = pd.read_csv(f, sep="\t")
4     return expand(
5       "results/processed/{sample}.txt",
6       sample=qc[qc["some-value"] > 90.0]["sample"]
7     )
8
9 rule all:
10  input:
11    get_results
12
13 checkpoint qc:
14   input:
15     expand("results/preprocessed/{sample}.txt", sample=samples)
16   output:
17     "results/qc.tsv"
18   shell:
19     "perform-qc {input} > {output}"
20
21 rule process:
22   input:
23     "results/preprocessed/{sample}.txt"
24   output:
25     "results/processed/{sample}.txt"
26   shell:
27     "process {input} > {output}"

f
1 rule step:
2   input:
3     "data/{sample}.txt"
4   output:
5     "results/{sample}.txt"
6   benchmark:
7     "benchmarks/some-tool/{sample}.txt"
8   shell:
9     "some-tool {input} > {output}"

```

Figure S1: Additional design patterns for Snakemake workflows. For brevity only rule properties that are necessary to understand each example are shown (e.g. omitting log directives and shell commands). (a) scatter/gather process, (b) streaming, (c) non-file parameters, (d) sample sheet based configuration, (e) conditional execution, (f) benchmarking. See section S2 for details.

Sample sheet based configuration (Figure S1d). Often, scientific experiments entail multiple samples, for which meta-information is known (e.g. gender, tissue etc. in biomedicine). Portable encapsulated projects (PEPs, <https://pep.databio.org>) are an approach to standardize such information and provide them in a shareable format. Snakemake workflows can be directly integrated with PEPs, thereby allowing to configure them via meta-information that is contained in the sample sheets defined by the PEP. Here, a pepfile (line 1) along with a validation schema (line 2) is defined, followed by an aggregation over all samples defined in the contained sample sheet.

Conditional execution (Figure S1e). By default, Snakemake determines the entire DAG of jobs upfront, before the first job is executed. However, sometimes the analysis path that shall be taken depends on some intermediate results. For example, this is the case when filtering samples based on quality control criteria. At the beginning of the data analysis, some quality control (QC) step is performed, which yields QC values for each sample. The actual analysis that shall happen afterwards might be only suitable for samples that pass the QC. Hence, one might have to filter out samples that do not pass the QC. Since the QC is an intermediate result of the same data analysis, it can be necessary to determine the part of the DAG that comes downstream of the QC only after QC has been finalized. Of course, one option is to separate QC and the actual analysis into two workflows, or defining a separate target rule for QC, such that it can be manually completed upfront, before the actual analysis is started. Alternatively, if QC shall happen automatically as part of the whole workflow, one can make use of Snakemake's conditional execution capabilities. In the example, we define that the `qc` rule shall be a so-called **checkpoint**. Rules can depend on such checkpoints by obtaining their output from a global `checkpoints` object (line 2), that is accessed inside of a function, which is passed to the `input` directive of the rule (line 11). This function is re-evaluated after the checkpoint has been executed (and its output files are present), thereby allowing to inspect the content of the checkpoint's output files, and decide about the input files based on that. In this example, the checkpoint rule `qc` creates a TSV file, which the function loads, in order to extract only those samples for which the column `"some-value"` contains a value greater than 90 (line 6). Only for those samples, the file `"results/processed/{sample}.txt"` is requested, which is then generated by applying the rule `process` for each of these samples.

Benchmarking (Figure S1f) Sometimes, a data analysis entails the benchmarking of certain tools in terms of runtime, CPU, and memory consumption. Snakemake directly supports such benchmarking by defining a `benchmark` directive in a rule (line 7). This directive takes a path to a TSV file. Upon execution of a job spawned from such a rule, Snakemake will constantly measure CPU and memory consumption, and store averaged results together with runtime information into the given TSV file. Benchmark files can be input to other rules, for example in order to generate plots or summary statistics.

S3 Scheduling: Further Considerations

While the first releases of Snakemake used a greedy scheduler, the current implementation aims at using more efficient schedules by solving a mixed integer linear program (MILP) whenever there are free resources. The current implementation already works well; still, future releases may consider additional objectives:

- The current formulation leads to fast removal of existing temporary files. In addition, one may control creation of temporary files in the first place, such that only limited space is occupied by temporary files at any time point during workflow execution.
- It may also be beneficial to initially identify bottleneck jobs in the graph and prioritize them automatically instead of relying on the workflow author to prioritize them.

Because we consider different objectives hierarchically and use large constants in the objective function, currently a high solver precision is needed. If more objectives are considered in the future, an alternative hierarchical formulation may be used: First find the optimal objective value for the first (or the first two) objectives; then solve another MILP that maximizes less important objectives and ensures via constraints that the optimality of the most important objective(s) is not violated, or stays within, say, 5% of the optimal value.

We also need to mention a technical detail about the interaction between the scheduler and streams (section S2). Some jobs that take part in handling a data stream may effectively use zero cores (because they mostly wait for data and then only read or write data), i.e. they have $u_{c,j} = 0$ in the MILP notation, which means that they do not contribute to the objective function. We thus replace the MILP objective term that maximizes parallelization ($\sum_{j \in J} u_{c,j} \cdot x_j$) by the modified term $\sum_{j \in J} \max\{u_{c,j}, 1\} \cdot x_j$ to ensure that the weight of any x_j within the sum is at least 1.

S4 Performance

When executing a data analysis workflow, running time and resource usage is dominated by the executed jobs and the performance of the libraries and tools used in these. Nevertheless, Snakemake has to process dependencies between jobs, which can incur some startup time until the actual workflow is executed. In order to provide an estimate on the amount of time and memory needed for this computation, we took the example workflow from Figure 3 in the main manuscript and artificially inflated it by replicating the countries in the input dataset. By this, we generated workflows of 10 to 90,000 jobs. Then, we benchmarked runtime and memory usage of Snakemake for computing the entire graph of jobs on these on a single core of an Intel Core i5 CPU with 1.6 GHz, 8 GB RAM and a Lenovo PCIe SSD (LENSE20512GMSP34MEAT2TA) (Figure S2). It can be seen that both runtime and memory increase linearly, starting from 0.2 seconds with 2.88 MB for 11 jobs and reaching 60 seconds with 1.1 GB for 90,000 jobs.

Figure S2: Runtime and memory usage of Snakemake while building the graph of jobs depending on the number of jobs in the workflow.

For future releases of Snakemake, we plan to further improve performance, for example by making use of PyPy (<https://www.pypy.org>), and by caching dependency resolution results between subsequent invocations of Snakemake.